

Cultural representation in English language textbooks: A comparative study of local and international editions

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Following the Islamic Revolution in 1979, Iran revised its English language education strategy, customising English Language Teaching (ELT) resources to better align with local contexts. This study examines cultural representation in locally-developed (*Eight, The ILLI, and Merit*) and internationally-published English language textbooks (*World English, Top Notch, and Four Corners*). Employing a mixed-methods design and frameworks by Moran (2001), Chao (2011), and Dahmardeh & Kim (2020), 58 textbooks were purposively sampled. Quantitative content analysis assessed the frequency and types of cultural elements, while qualitative thematic analysis provided deeper insights into the cultural dimensions represented. Findings indicate that locally-developed textbooks incorporate more local cultural perspectives, whereas international textbooks emphasise cultural products. Both types equally represent cultural practices and persons. The study underscores the importance of incorporating diverse cultural elements in ELT textbooks to promote intercultural competence, offering practical recommendations for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers.

Keywords: Cultural Representation; Cultural Dimensions; Intercultural Awareness; Intercultural Competence; Textbook Evaluation

1. Introduction

Technological advancements and globalisation have significantly increased cross-cultural communication (Dahmardeh & Kim, 2020), establishing English as a global lingua franca (Jenkins, 2018). Scholars argue that teaching language without considering its cultural context is ineffective, as language and culture are intrinsically linked (Hilliard, 2014). This connection is critical in the development of educational materials that foster intercultural competence among learners.

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Following the Islamic Revolution in 1979, Iran underwent a series of educational reforms aimed at reinforcing national identity while enhancing English language proficiency to facilitate effective global communication. This period also raised concerns about the potential influence of imperialistic ideas embedded in foreign textbooks (Aliakbari, 2004). In contrast, locally-developed materials often present culturally biased representations that align more closely with national values.

This study conducts a comprehensive analysis and comparison of locally-developed and internationally-published ELT textbooks, focusing on cultural dimensions such as (a) perspectives, (b) products, (c) practices, and (d) persons. By examining these cultural elements, the research aims to enhance learners' cultural competence through improved educational materials that reflect the reciprocal influence of culture in various disciplines.

The primary objective of this research is to underscore the pivotal role of textbooks in cultivating intercultural competence. The study offers valuable insights for educators, curriculum designers, and policymakers in the development of culturally sensitive ELT materials. It assumes that addressing cultural representation in ELT textbooks not only contributes to the academic discourse on ELT and globalisation but also highlights the importance of equipping individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge to thrive in diverse and multicultural communities.

By providing a detailed analysis of cultural representations in both locally-developed and international textbooks, this research seeks to inform and guide the creation of ELT resources that promote a balanced and inclusive view of global cultures. This research aims to address a gap in the literature by comparing the cultural dimensions present in the selected textbooks across various academic contexts. The major research questions of the study include:

- (1) How do locally-developed ELT textbooks represent different dimensions of culture?
- (2) How do international ELT textbooks represent different dimensions of culture?
- (3) Are there significant differences in the representation of cultural dimensions between locally-developed and international textbooks?

2. Background

2.1. Conceptualising culture

The concept of culture is multifaceted and dynamic, encompassing diverse definitions across academic disciplines. Early scholars like Matthew Arnold (1822-1888) and Edward Tylor (1832-1917), cited in Goodrich (2020), offered

contrasting views—Arnold focusing on elite intellectual pursuits and Tylor on inclusive social customs. Franz Boas (1858-1942), as cited in Kuper (1999), introduced cultural relativism, emphasising context-specific beliefs and customs. Kroeber and Kluckhohn (1952) provided a comprehensive definition of culture, encompassing all aspects of human existence that are transmitted through symbols. Edward Hall (1966) introduced the metaphor of the iceberg to illustrate the observable and hidden components of culture.

Contemporary scholars, such as Peterson and Coltrane (2003), place particular emphasis on the significance of communication and rituals in the study of culture. Richards & Schmidt (2014) and Brown (2014) view culture as practices, codes, and values unique to specific groups, fostering shared beliefs and identities within communities. The integral role of language in shaping and transmitting culture underscores its importance in cultural education (Hall, 1997). Understanding the interconnectedness of language and culture is crucial for comprehensive cultural education and future research (Hinkel, 1999).

2.2. Evolution of culture in ELT textbooks

Despite the increasing prevalence of digital resources, textbooks continue to play a pivotal role in language education, second only to teachers in terms of their influence on student achievement (Riazi, 2003; Weninger & Kiss, 2013). They provide essential structure and content, functioning as the backbone of the curriculum (Richards, 2017; Tomlinson, 2023). ELT textbooks have evolved significantly, initially focusing solely on linguistic competence with minimal cultural context (Kramersch, 1998). They now recognise the importance of intercultural understanding in the context of globalisation and new learning theories (Kramersch, 2013).

Cultural content in ELT textbooks can be understood through three perspectives: globalisation, localisation, and glocalisation. Globalisation advocates exploring diverse cultural elements worldwide to promote intercultural proficiency (Alptekin, 2002). Localisation suggests including the native culture of the target language, making materials more relatable within learners' own cultural contexts (Kramersch, 1998; Widdowson, 1998). Glocalisation combines local and global elements, addressing the needs of learners in diverse settings while nurturing both local and global identities (Xu, 2010).

With 80% of global English communication occurring among non-native speakers (Sharifian, 2013), ELT materials must reflect this reality. Integrating 'glocal' cultural content can prepare learners for real-world communication and enhance intercultural sensitivity (Gray, 2002). However, globally distributed textbooks often inadequately incorporate intercultural competence and neglect

local cultural elements (Abdul Rahim & Jalalian Daghigh, 2020). Therefore, a balanced approach that includes both local and global perspectives is recommended for developing effective and engaging ELT materials.

2.3. Cultural evaluation of ELT textbooks

Textbook evaluation is a systematic procedure aimed at assessing educational materials to ensure alignment with curriculum objectives and learner needs (Tomlinson, 2023). Sheldon (1988) highlights its dual purpose: assisting educators in selecting appropriate instructional resources, and enhancing awareness of a textbook's strengths and weaknesses. Textbook evaluation is a form of 'action research' that deepens understanding of teaching materials and supports teachers' professional development (Pan & Zhu, 2022).

Weninger (2021) examines textbook evaluation in language teaching from two main perspectives. Firstly, textbooks are viewed as tools for facilitating language acquisition in classrooms, guided by language acquisition theories to meet diverse learner needs (Tomlinson, 2023). Secondly, textbooks are considered cultural and curricular artefacts that contain shared knowledge and meaning, necessitating recognition and mitigation of any cultural biases (Weninger, 2021).

The abundance of ELT resources has made selecting effective textbooks challenging due to pedagogical deficiencies that hinder language acquisition (Litz, 2005). Therefore, careful selection is crucial across educational levels (Ellis, 1997). Ellis underscores the importance of using checklists and frameworks for thorough textbook evaluation tailored to specific educational contexts.

2.4. Analysing cultural representation in ELT textbooks

Representation in language plays a crucial role in shaping meaning and facilitating communication (Hall, 1997). It encompasses how the world is depicted, and messages are transmitted. Language acts as a system of representation, conveying shared meanings and contributing to cultural development. Influenced by societal ideologies, representations significantly shape discourses and cultural realities within educational resources like textbooks.

Textbooks are considered as "curriculum selections," with the cultural representations within them being seen as "normative cultural selections of content from what, in theory, is a virtually unlimited set of possible selections" (Luke, 2015, p. 214). They not only function as channels for the transmission of societal perspectives and behaviours, but also as repositories for cultural characteristics that embody prevailing norms, values, and attitudes (Canale,

2016). Each element contained within these materials holds cultural importance, conveying cultural knowledge through written texts, tasks, and images (Adaskou et al., 1990).

The presence or absence of cultural content in teaching materials reflects the beliefs of textbook authors and the values they support (Tickoo, 1995). Recent studies highlight the significance of diverse cultural representation in textbooks for successful language acquisition. However, many textbooks still lack sufficient cultural content. Assessing textbooks from a cultural standpoint increases educators' and researchers' understanding, providing deeper insights into their contribution to language education.

Numerous studies have examined the cultural content present in ELT textbooks across various nations. Bose and Gao (2022) have highlighted the strong influence of postcolonialism and globalisation within Indian textbooks. Conversely, Jorfi et al. (2022) have identified deficiencies in the comprehensive representation of culture within Iranian and Egyptian textbooks. Dolgunsöz and Yiğit (2022) have conducted an analysis of Iranian and Turkish textbooks, revealing biases towards the source culture in Iranian textbooks and the target culture in Turkish textbooks. Hassaskhah and Abdollahi (2021) have discovered a prevailing Western bias within ELT textbooks, while Dahmardeh and Kim (2020) have observed an excessive focus on the source culture within Iranian textbooks. Collectively, these studies emphasise the significant disparities and imbalances in cultural representation, influenced by geopolitical and social contexts.

2. 5. Dimensions of culture

Perspectives: The worldviews held by individuals within a community have a profound impact on behaviours and identities in cultural activities, communicating specific perceptions, values, and beliefs (Yuen, 2011). These perspectives encompass significant cultural elements such as important dates and events, judgmental statements, stereotypes, values and beliefs, social class and occupations, disability and discrimination, and proverbs (Dahmardeh & Kim, 2020), each of which is crucial in defining cultural identity and guiding societal norms.

Important dates and events shape a nation's history, reinforce collective memories, and preserve cultural heritage (Frost & Laing, 2011). Ceremonies and celebrations related to these events also promote cultural preservation, societal unity, and offer insights into societal responses to challenges. Etiquette varies across cultures, shaped by cultural values and norms (Salmani Nodoushan, 2019), playing a critical role in fostering respectful intercultural communication and reducing conflicts.

Similarly, judgemental statements convey personal beliefs and attitudes (Dahmardeh & Kim, 2020), perpetuating cultural biases and hindering effective communication. Stereotyping categorises individuals based on group membership, attributing generalised characteristics that foster prejudice and discrimination (Bonner, 1999). Values are conceptual frameworks that define cultural practices and norms, establishing moral codes and identities, while beliefs are subjective truths contributing to cultural identity (Gelfand et al., 2011).

Social class and occupations categorise individuals by access to resources like wealth, education, and professional status (Heena, 2022). Additionally, disability includes physical impairments and socioeconomic challenges, influenced by societal norms and values (Forstner, 2022). Discrimination involves unequal treatment based on factors such as race, colour, religion, age, disability, and gender. Finally, proverbs, as concise sayings, reflect cultural values, beliefs, and historical experiences, serving as moral guidelines and transmitting cultural virtues to younger generations (Mieder, 2008).

Products: Products are artefacts created or embraced by members of a culture, encompassing aspects such as family, food, travel, tourism, politics, economy, history, geography, literature, art, architecture, education, sports, race, places, religion, clothing, groups, organisations, merchandise products, and characters (Damardeh & Kim, 2020).

Families, as long-standing institutions, hold a pivotal position in uniting personal and societal aspects crucial for procreation, socialisation, and the preservation of cultural traditions (Brown et al., 2020). Food and dietary practices provide a means to examine societal structures, historical changes, and power dynamics (Parasecoli, 2019). Additionally, travel and tourism commodify cultural values while acting as platforms for preserving and exchanging cultural elements, promoting intercultural understanding and global interconnectedness (Madandola & Boussaa, 2023). Politics encompasses the acquisition of power, governance, and authority within societies, heavily influenced by cultural factors shaping political identities and behaviours. Political systems also shape national and international cultural policies, influencing a country's identity and global reputation (Strunc, 2019). The economy involves the production, exchange, and utilisation of goods and services across local and international markets. Economic values shape consumption behaviours, work attitudes, and business principles (Yu, 2022).

History documents significant events that shape cultural identity and societal structures, while geography explores how human activities interact with the physical environment, influenced by factors like terrain, climate, and natural resources (Becker, 2016; Lane et al., 2019).

Literature, art, and architecture reflect cultural values, traditions, and societal advancements. They capture historical events, societal nuances, and emotional expression, preserving cultural heritage through various mediums (Ashadi, 2020; Khan, 2021). In the same vein, education plays a crucial role in acquiring knowledge, transmitting cultural values, facilitating socialisation, and shaping societal norms. Moreover, sports enhance physical well-being, foster social cohesion, and form community identity, deeply intertwined with cultural values and traditions.

Ethnicity and race denote an individual's association with a specific social group, reflecting shared ancestry, history, values, and beliefs (Worrell, 2015). Places, including cities, buildings, and houses, express values, and historical narratives. Their design symbolises societal aspirations, shaping cultural landscapes (Hall, 1966). Religion encompasses belief in divine entities, structured worship practices, and influences societal customs and artistic expressions, promoting mutual understanding and reducing discrimination (Almutawaa, 2023).

Clothing communicates cultural identities, social hierarchies, and historical contexts (Batra, 2019). Formal organisations and informal groups shape cultural norms and behaviours within societies (Celikdemir, 2023). Merchandising promotes cultural aesthetics and heritage preservation through promotional activities and product design (Taneja, et al., 2023).

Practices: Practices encompass customary actions and interactions within specific cultural contexts, including customs, cultural norms, holidays, myths, legends and entertainment (Dahmardeh & Kim, 2020). Customs are habitual practices reflecting deeply ingrained values, fostering community unity, and providing insights into core principles (Hall, 1976). Cultural norms, including folkways, mores, taboos, and laws, regulate behaviours and standards, influencing interactions from informal expectations to formal rules (Shweder, 1991). Holidays celebrate significant events, fostering cultural identity and promoting belonging (Scheer, 2022). Myths and legends transmit values and traditions, while entertainment provides pleasurable experiences through various activities (Arvind, 2022).

Persons: Culture can be elucidated through the representation of notable figures and ordinary persons (Moran, 2001). Dahmardeh and Kim (2020) categorised person into famous people, first names, and family names.

Famous people gain recognition through exceptional achievements, influencing and reflecting societal values and norms. Their fame preserves cultural heritage, promotes societal ideals, and fosters national pride (Osterman & Brown, 2011). First names, given at birth, reflect cultural customs

and societal values, conveying social information about gender, age, group affiliation, and cultural background influenced by traditions, norms, and religious beliefs. Similarly, family names hold significant cultural importance, indicating heritage, traditions, and societal values. They range from ancestral lineage in East Asian cultures to occupational or locational origins in the Western world (Yu, 2019).

3. Method

This study examines cultural representation within 58 ELT textbooks, including three locally-developed and three internationally recognised series widely used in accredited Iranian ELT institutes. The purposive selection criteria considered (a) learner population, (b) cultural content, (c) novelty, and (d) relevance. Two locally produced series (*Eight* and *Merit*) and one international textbook (*World English*) are recent publications not previously evaluated for cultural content. This research aims to address a gap in the literature by comparing the cultural dimensions present in these textbooks across various academic contexts. The research questions addressed in the study include the following:

- (1) How do locally-developed ELT textbooks represent different dimensions of culture? This question aims to explore the cultural content in textbooks produced within a specific country or region. It is crucial because it can shed light on how local contexts, values, and cultural aspects are integrated into language teaching materials. Understanding this can help in evaluating the relevance and relatability of these textbooks to the students who use them.
- (2) How do international ELT textbooks represent different dimensions of culture? This question seeks to investigate the cultural representation in globally marketed textbooks. Such textbooks often aim for a broad appeal and might incorporate diverse cultural elements to cater to a wide audience. Analysing these textbooks can reveal how effectively they manage to include and balance different cultural perspectives, which is important for promoting cultural awareness and sensitivity among learners.
- (3) Are there significant differences in the representation of cultural dimensions between locally-developed and international textbooks? This comparative question is very insightful as it aims to identify and understand the differences and similarities between local and international ELT materials. It can provide valuable information on whether international textbooks are adaptable to local contexts or if locally-developed textbooks offer more culturally relevant content.

Such a comparison can inform educators and policymakers in making better choices regarding textbook selection.

3.1. Materials

The locally-developed English language textbook series include *Eight*, (1st Edition, 2019), which is in alignment with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). This series is published by the Academic Centre for Education, Culture, and Research (ACECR) and has received certification from York Press. Currently, it is being used in over 200 branches. Another widely utilised series in Iran is the new editions of *ILI* (2017) textbooks, which have been developed by the Iran Language Institute. This series caters to more than 1,200,000 learners annually across 290 branches. Furthermore, there is a newly published series called *Merit* (2023), which places a special emphasis on Iranian culture and Islamic principles.

The internationally published English language textbook series aligned with the CEFR includes *World English* (3rd Edition, 2023), featuring updated content with authentic language materials and narratives from National Geographic and TED. *Top Notch* (3rd Edition, 2016), recognised for 'Textbook Excellence' by the 'Textbook Academic Authors Association' (TAA), emphasises diverse accents and cultural backgrounds, published by Pearson. *Four Corners* (2nd Edition, 2019), authored by Jack C. Richards and David Bohlke and published by Cambridge University Press, integrates East Asian characters and themes, offering a broad spectrum of cultural perspectives.

3.2. Procedure

The study employs a mixed-methods approach, which integrates both qualitative and quantitative methodologies to evaluate the representation of cultural content in texts, tasks, and images, using comprehensive frameworks developed by Moran (2001), Chao (2011), and Dahmardeh and Kim (2020). These frameworks offer a broader examination of cultural elements compared to commonly used such as Hofstede, Tucker, Kachru, Chambers, Garinger, Miekley, Littlejohn, Adaskou et al, Weninger and Kiss, Sercu, Cortazzi, and Jin. This comprehensive approach is particularly advantageous for analysing ELT textbooks and promoting intercultural competence among learners.

The analysis encompasses content analysis, a reliable and objective approach in educational research (Cohen et al., 2017). It involves systematic coding of themes, identification of patterns, and construction of theoretical frameworks (Weninger & Kiss, 2013). Recurrent cultural themes were identified and coded, and their frequencies were calculated and converted into percentages. Subsequently, statistical methods were employed to analyse the data, and the findings were presented through charts and tables.

The researchers achieved a high level of inter-rater reliability by engaging an expert in Applied Linguistics, conducting independent content analyses, and resolving any disparities through discussions. They used Cohen's kappa coefficient and achieved an agreement level of 0.82, which falls under the classification of "almost perfect" according to Landis and Koch (1977). This exceeds the 0.70 threshold for reliable content analysis, thereby significantly enhancing the validity and reliability of the study's findings regarding cultural representation in ELT textbooks.

Due to the subjective nature of visual content, coders achieved consensus through discussions on physical attributes, clothing, and depicted objects. In order to ensure accuracy, they consulted supplementary resources, including Google, online encyclopaedias, and Google Lens. Additionally, items that fell into multiple categories were classified based on their contextual relevance, and were only counted once.

4. Results

4.1. Locally-developed textbooks

Perspectives: The examination of the perspectives uncovered a notable focus on social class and occupations (42.8%). Values and beliefs (33%) were also prominently emphasised. Additional aspects included judgemental statements (10%), social etiquette (7.7%), proverbs (2.4%), important dates and events (2.2%), disability and discrimination (1.6%), and stereotypes (0.3%).

Products: The examination of cultural products unveils a significant concentration on education (17.2%), family (13.5%), and economy (12.5%). Additionally, geography (10%), literature, art, architecture (8.2%), sports (7%), places (6.7%), travel, and tourism (5.5%) emerge as prominent themes. Conversely, less attention is given to race (4.3%), clothing (4.2%), food (2.8%), politics (2.3%), religion (1.7%), groups and organisations (1.5%), history (1.2%), merchandise products, and characters (1%).

Practices: The analysis of cultural practices revealed a particular emphasis on cultural norms (34.3%) and entertainment (33.5%). Moreover, the investigation encompassed myths and legends (18%), customs (9%), and holidays (5.2%).

Persons: The exploration of persons highlights a significant focus on first names (74.1%). Furthermore, there is a considerable presence of prominent figures (16.7%). However, last names (9.2%) are mentioned less frequently.

All in all, locally-developed textbooks place significant emphasis on products as the most extensively discussed aspect, followed closely by persons, albeit to a slightly lesser degree. Perspectives also attract substantial attention. In

contrast, practices are the least scrutinised and receive the least amount of attention among the analysed dimensions.

4.2. International textbooks

Perspectives: The analysis revealed a strong focus on social class and occupations (52.4%), with significant emphasis on values and beliefs (19.8%) and social etiquette (13.6%). Nonetheless, judgemental statements (8.5%), proverbs (4.2%), disability and discrimination (1%), and important dates and events (0.4%) received minimal consideration. It is worth noting that stereotypes were virtually absent from the textbooks.

Products: The analysis of cultural products in the textbooks unveiled a plethora of themes. Geography (12.8%), places (12.7%), and travel and tourism (12%) emerged as the most commonly examined subjects. Literature, art and architecture (10%), education (9.8%), and family (8.6%) also occupied a significant position, providing insights into cultural manifestation and societal dynamics. Economic factors (7.2%), sports (5.7%), food (5.2%), clothing (4.6%), and race and ethnicity (4.2%) followed closely behind. Conversely, groups and organisations (2.7%), politics (2.7%), merchandise products and characters (2.1%), history (1.4%), and religion (0.4%) received relatively limited consideration.

Practices: Cultural practices were prominently highlighted in the textbooks, with a particular emphasis on entertainment (56%) as the central topic of discussion. Additionally, customs (26%) and cultural norms (10%) were thoroughly examined, although holidays (6.5%), and myths and legends (3.5%) received comparatively less attention.

Persons: The representation of persons in the textbooks was predominantly focused on their first names (75%), with family names (14.5%) and famous people (10.5%) ranking second and third, respectively.

As for international textbooks, our analysis highlights 'products' as the most discussed subject, with 'persons' following closely as the second most addressed dimension. 'Perspectives' are noted as another significant aspect, while 'practices' receive the least emphasis among the examined dimensions. As such, locally-developed and international textbooks apparently mirror each other.

5. Comparative analysis

A one-way between-groups analysis of variance was run for the comparative analysis between locally-developed and international textbooks in terms of the representation of cultural dimensions. ANOVA results revealed no statistically significant differences [$F(1, 208) = 2.08; p = 0.151; Eta^2 = .009$].

It is important to highlight that textbooks developed at the local level tend to prioritise cultural perspectives to a greater extent than international textbooks, although this disparity did not reach statistical significance. Moreover, locally-developed textbooks display a lesser representation of cultural products, while both types exhibited a similar representation of cultural practices and person. For a comprehensive analysis of the cultural dimensions in locally-developed versus international textbooks, see Table 1.

Table 1

Dimensions of Culture in Locally-Developed vs. International Textbooks

Cultural Dimensions	Local		International	
	Count	%	Count	%
(1) Perspectives	10374	24	4986	17.5
(2) Products	18332	42.4	14778	52
(3) Practices	3849	8.9	2184	7.7
(4) Persons	10697	24.7	6497	22.8
Total	43252	100	28445	100

6. Discussion

6.1. Locally-developed versus international textbooks

Perspectives: In both locally-developed and international textbooks, there is a noticeable emphasis on societal structures, hierarchies, and professional roles, with the aim of familiarising students with the diversity and dynamics of various occupations. Locally-developed textbooks prioritise Iranian values such as hospitality, respect, and honesty in accordance with the findings of Dahmardeh and Kim (2020) and Jorfi et al. (2022), while international textbooks place greater emphasis on global values and beliefs, aligning with the findings of Hassaskhah and Abdollahi (2021). Both types of textbooks incorporate judgemental statements to encourage critical thinking and deepen understanding of social dynamics.

International textbooks extensively discuss social etiquette and manners, highlighting customary behaviours across diverse cultural contexts. This indicates a stronger global emphasis compared to Iranian educational materials. Proverbs also play a significant role in international textbooks, serving as vehicles for transmitting cultural values and fostering cultural understanding. Important historical dates and events are another focal point, shaping collective memory and identity that are emphasised in international textbooks.

However, despite their academic importance, topics related to inclusivity, diversity, and social justice—such as disability and discrimination—receive

inadequate attention in current textbooks. The minimal presence of stereotypes suggests a deliberate effort to promote cultural sensitivity and avoid simplistic representations that perpetuate bias. This lack of focus may originate from cultural biases, commercial constraints, and curriculum standards (Hassaskhah & Abdollahi, 2021). Subsequent textbooks could rectify these deficiencies by incorporating diverse perspectives.

Products: Locally-developed textbooks place a strong emphasis on education as a central aspect of cultural discourse in Iran. They cover a wide range of academic disciplines and highlight the importance of knowledge dissemination within Iranian society. This emphasis on education is indicative of the profound societal respect for intellectual accomplishments and knowledge within Iranian society. Economy is highlighted in these textbooks reflecting the Iranian attitudes towards wealth, economic ideologies, and societal values associated with prosperity.

Both locally-developed and international textbooks incorporate geographical elements, such as countries, mountains, and rivers, to provide contextual information. They also emphasise the significant role of the family in shaping cultural identity, reinforcing the importance of family structures and relationships in personal and cultural development. Locally-developed textbooks provide extensive coverage of literature, art, and architecture, underscoring their profound importance in Iranian culture. References include classic Persian poets (like Saadi), renowned Iranian carpets, and iconic landmarks (such as Persepolis), helping students appreciate their rich cultural heritage and develop a sense of national pride. Similarly, both types of textbooks dedicate sections to sports, promoting health and fostering social interactions. Notable locations, such as cities, buildings, and houses, are extensively discussed in both types of textbooks.

Travel and tourism topics are present in all textbooks, with international ones offering more extensive coverage of cultural heritage sites that help enhance students' global awareness. In both textbooks, references to various ethnic backgrounds and racial identities underline the significance of cultural diversity and the need for understanding racial dynamics. Similarly, cultural attire and fashion trends, such as the Iranian Chador, the Korean Hanbok, and the Indian Sari, are highlighted as symbols of societal norms, regional identities, religious convictions, and historical influences that, in turn, help students understand the role of clothing in expressing identity. Additionally, students are introduced to diverse culinary concepts through references to food preferences like Iranian Kebab, Basbousa, pizza, and vegetarian options.

Locally-developed textbooks frequently refer to Islamic traditions and philanthropic efforts, topics that receive less emphasis in international textbooks, possibly due to marketability concerns. Political matters are

sporadically represented with examples such as the Iranian revolution in 1979 or discussions about conservative and liberal ideologies in both textbooks. The inclusion of organisations such as UNESCO and the Red Cross in textbooks promotes global citizenship and enhances students' understanding of humanitarian efforts. Although references to specific historical events are limited, they introduce students to significant incidents. Consumer goods such as the "SmartScan" app and "Benz" automobile are included to accurately depict contemporary societies and consumer trends.

The emphasis placed on different cultural products in textbooks greatly influences students' learning and understanding of various cultures. Being exposed to a wide range of cultural elements has the potential to broaden students' horizons, foster critical thinking, and nurture cultural empathy.

Practices: Locally-developed textbooks in Iran place a significant emphasis on cultural norms, such as 'refraining from backbiting'. This underscores the anticipated behaviours and societal standards that are claimed to be probably exclusive to Iranian society. This focus underscores the significance of cultural identity and societal values within the educational context. In contrast, international textbooks often prioritise elements of popular culture such as films, music, and contemporary lifestyles, providing students with a dynamic and engaging approach to language learning that reflects global trends.

Furthermore, Iranian educational materials often incorporate myths, legends, and folklore extensively to safeguard cultural narratives and historical heritage. For instance, a prevalent belief suggests that one should pour a bowl of water onto the ground behind a person embarking on a journey, as a symbolic act of ensuring their safe return. Conversely, international textbooks offer a comprehensive exploration of global customs and traditions, aiming to broaden students' perspectives beyond national boundaries as supported by Hassaskhah and Abdollahi's (2021) research. However, locally-developed textbooks also highlight specific Iranian customs and traditions, such as the celebration of 'Yalda Night' or 'Shab-e-Chelleh', which symbolises community and continuity among cultural change. These cultural festivals, along with national holidays and religious observances, like Nowruz and Eid al-Adha, play a crucial role in fostering solidarity and reinforcing cultural identity within the local context.

Anyway, while both types of textbooks acknowledge the importance of cultural heritage and identity, they differ significantly in their approach and emphasis. Locally-developed textbooks prioritise Iranian cultural norms and traditions, while international textbooks offer a broader global practice. The inclusion of Iranian cultural norms and traditions in locally-produced textbooks is crucial for enhancing students' cultural competency. By emphasising these elements, students can gain a better understanding of societal values and identity. This

emphasis also enriches their language acquisition by providing contextually relevant material. Moreover, exposure to diverse global customs through international textbooks broadens students' perspectives and increases their intercultural sensitivity.

Persons: The significant emphasis placed on first names underscores their cultural importance and their role in shaping individual identities within diverse cultural contexts. 'Muhammad' and 'Sara' are universal and prevalent among many nations. Locally-developed textbooks place significant emphasis on influential figures, including Abul-Qasem Ferdowsi and Takhti, as well as other renowned global personalities. This comprehensive inclusion highlights the importance of honouring notable individuals while nurturing students' curiosity, empathy, and global consciousness. On the contrary, international textbooks place greater emphasis on the significance of family names compared to local textbooks.

However, despite offering a comprehensive exploration of diverse aspects, certain subdimensions such as disability, discrimination, history, merchandise products, politics, religion, and ethnic diversity are insufficiently addressed. Enhancing these areas will improve students' comprehension of diverse cultures and equip them for effective engagement in a pluralistic and globalised society. To effectively address these underrepresented themes, it is suggested that textbooks incorporate narratives, case studies, discussion questions, and group projects that focus on these subjects.

6.2. Comparison between local and international textbooks

Like we said above, the ANOVA analysis was conducted to compare cultural dimensions in locally-developed and international textbooks. The obtained F-value was 2.080, and the corresponding significance level was 0.151, indicating a non-significant result. This implies that there are no statistically significant differences in the representation of cultural dimensions between these two types of textbooks. Both locally-developed and international textbooks appear to present perspectives, products, practices, and persons in a somewhat similar manner.

The lack of significant differences suggests that both locally-developed and international textbooks aim to provide a comprehensive representation of cultural dimensions, reflecting a growing recognition of inclusivity and global worldviews in language education. Moreover, it highlights the recognition of the crucial role played by cultural diversity in fostering students' intercultural competencies. Consequently, these findings imply a shift towards a standardised approach to the representation of cultures in diverse educational contexts, with the intention of equipping students with the essential skills to actively engage with diverse societies in the progressively globalised world.

7. Conclusion

Contrary to most studies conducted globally and in Iran (Abdul Rahim & Jalalian Daghigh, 2020; Bose & Gao, 2022; Dahmardeh & Kim, 2020; Dolgunsöz & Yiğit, 2022; Jorfi et al., 2022; Hassaskhah & Abdollahi, 2021; and others found in their studies), there are no significant differences between locally-developed and international textbooks. While statistically insignificant differences exist in overall cultural representation between locally-developed and international textbooks, noticeable patterns can still be observed.

Locally-developed textbooks tend to place greater emphasis on perspectives, particularly values and beliefs. By prioritising these concepts, authors aim to establish the foundation of cultural norms and practices (Gelfand et al., 2011). Values such as honesty, respect, and social responsibility establish moral benchmarks, while beliefs such as religious faith, hospitality, the significance of education, and reverence for elders make substantial contributions to cultural identities. Emphasising fundamental local values enhances the quality of students' education.

International textbooks offer extensive exposure to diverse global cultures through various cultural aspects like travel, tourism, architectural design, urban planning, and food practices, promoting cultural exchange and global interconnectedness. This approach fosters critical thinking, intercultural sensitivity, and a comprehensive appreciation of global diversity, preparing students for effective navigation in an interconnected world.

Although both series of textbooks cover practices similarly, locally-developed textbooks are distinguished by their significant emphasis on cultural norms, myths, and legends. The authors aim to establish appropriate behaviours and standards within Iranian society by prioritising cultural norms, which encompass collective beliefs, values, and behaviours that impact interactions and actions, from informal expectations to formal regulations. Additionally, they seek to influence behaviour and aid in psychosocial adaptation by conveying moral and philosophical ideas (Jalali & Zandieh, 2022). By incorporating myths and legends, these textbooks foster cultural identity.

Finally, it is noteworthy that persons are treated similarly in both sets of textbooks. However, it is essential to emphasise that locally-developed textbooks place a significant emphasis on featuring famous people. This emphasis not only profoundly influences the shaping of societal values and cultural norms but also serves as a reflection of them. By celebrating these renowned figures, the preservation of cultural heritage takes priority, societal ideals are promoted, and a sense of national pride is nurtured.

To optimise students' learning outcomes, it is advised that educators adopt inclusive teaching strategies such as case studies and literature from diverse

backgrounds that incorporate both local and international perspectives into the curriculum. This pedagogical approach facilitates the development of a comprehensive understanding of national identity, while simultaneously fostering an appreciation for cultural diversity.

Additionally, policymakers hold a crucial responsibility in endorsing endeavours that enhance cultural inclusivity within educational systems, guaranteeing that textbooks and teaching methodologies accurately represent the cultural heritage and global perspectives. This can be achieved by inclusion of diverse cultures in textbooks, or by mandating teacher training programmes focusing on cultural sensitivity.

As the scope of the study is limited to textbooks used in Iranian ELT institutes, the generalisability of the findings may be affected. Further research could be conducted to examine the impact of multiculturalism on educational representation and scholarly pursuits through cross-cultural comparisons across various academic disciplines like history, literature, social studies, and even mathematics or science.

Authors' Statement

Both authors affirm that they collaborated on the discussion and creation of this work. Both authors came up with the concept, gathered the information, and worked on the manuscript, editing and refining it.

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